

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV

Full resource

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Introduction to the guide

Summary

Narrative CVs are important for qualitative assessment which should be the primary method for assessment of an individual researcher. A narrative CV can be an opportunity for a researcher to demonstrate a variety of contributions and activities, including Open Science (OS) contributions.

The aim of this guide is to provide tips for researchers on how to highlight their OS activities in an evidence-based narrative CV, especially when using the [Royal Society's template "Résumé for Researchers \(R4R\)"](#) or UKRI's [The Résumé for Research and Innovation \(R4RI\)](#). In addition, the link between responsible researcher assessment (RRA) and narrative CV is discussed from both from the perspective of researchers and research funders, the emphasis being on the latter.

Please note that this guide does not provide comprehensive instructions on how to write a narrative CV. However, we can highlight a few simple steps to begin with the following:

Try to avoid:

- repetition
- using acronyms or field specific jargon
- copy-pasting
- lists of e.g., publications

Instead:

- highlight your own unique contributions to research and society with your own words,
- use clear and concise language
- consider what the reviewer might be looking for.

For instructions on how to write a narrative CV, please see e.g., [DORA resource library](#), University of Oxford's resources on "[Developing a narrative CV: guidance for researchers](#)" and The Peer Exchange Platform for Narrative-style CVs ([PEP-CV](#)). Other useful resources are listed in the "Useful links" section.

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aims to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for

OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for the stages O and P.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Abbreviations and definitions

Evidence. "The reach, use, and relevance data in this block capture how the scholarly activities and their outputs are (a) affecting beneficiaries, (b) being shared and used, and (c) the relevance of this to stakeholders. It seeks to elicit both qualitative and quantitative data on what is different because these scholarly activities are in the world." (Lima & Bowman 2022).

Narrative CV. A narrative CV is "a type of CV format that provides structured written descriptions of academics' or researchers' contributions and achievements that reflect a broad range of relevant skills and experiences." (Fritch et al. 2024).

Open Science (OS). The [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (UNESCO 2021) has defined OS as follows: "Open science is a set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone for the benefit of scientists and society as a whole. Open science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that the production of that knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable."

The recommendation builds on the following four key pillars (see figure 2):

1. **Open scientific knowledge.** This pillar focuses on making all forms of scientific outputs, including publications, data, software, hardware, and educational resources, openly available and accessible to all.

2. **Open Science infrastructures.** These are shared physical or virtual resources, such as shared research infrastructures, that provide the necessary services and systems for members of the scientific community to practice open science.
3. **Open engagement of societal actors.** This pillar emphasizes the importance of including and involving society in the scientific process, ensuring participation and collaboration from different actors and communities.
4. **Open dialogue with other knowledge systems.** This component promotes an open and respectful exchange with other knowledge systems, such as indigenous and traditional knowledge, integrating diverse perspectives into scientific advancement.

Figure 2. UNESCO’s four key pillars of OS (UNESCO 2021).

Responsible researcher assessment RRA. Curry et al. (2020) define RRA as “umbrella term for approaches to assessment which incentivise, reflect and reward the plural characteristics of high-quality research, in support of diverse and inclusive research cultures.”

R4R. [Royal Society’s narrative CV template “Résumé for Researchers \(R4R\)”](#)

R4RI. UKRI’s narrative CV template [The Résumé for Research and Innovation \(R4RI\)](#).

How to provide evidence for OS contributions in a narrative CV

What does evidence mean in this context?

When talking about narrative CVs, the term “evidence-based” is often included. As stated in the Abbreviations and definitions section, Lima & Bowman (2022) define evidence as follows: *“The reach, use, and relevance data in this block capture how the scholarly activities and their outputs are (a) affecting beneficiaries, (b) being shared and used, and (c) the relevance of this to stakeholders. It seeks to elicit both qualitative and quantitative data on what is different because these scholarly activities are in the world.”*

Examples of evidence of the impact of journal articles can be, e.g.

- citations (note that indicators such as raw citation counts should be used responsibly; please see **GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168> for more details).
- altmetrics
- views and downloads
- comments and reviews

Examples of evidence of the impact of books or book chapters can be, e.g.

- altmetrics
- library holdings
- book reviews
- translations

Examples of evidence of the impact of datasets can be, e.g.

- data citations
- views and downloads
- altmetrics
- FAIRness of datasets

Please see Maastricht University library’s guide for [Evidence-Based Narrative CV](#) for further examples and tips.

- Please see also **GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Open science assessment guide** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630> and **GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>.

Specifying the openness and FAIRness can be used as **evidence of OS efforts**. The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles are most commonly used for research data management, but are suitable for all research outputs including publications, data, software etc.

It is also important to, e.g.

- assign licenses to outputs

Figure 3. Illustration of some potential OS activities in relation to different modules of the *Résumé for Researchers*.

Module 1 – Knowledge

Prompts:

- R4R: How have you contributed to the generation of knowledge?
- R4RI: Contributions to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies or knowledge

Tips:

- Demonstrate with concrete examples your commitment to open and transparent research practices throughout the research process, including in how you manage and share data, methods, and findings.
- You can also include reasoning for practicing responsibility in OS, e.g., sharing only parts or metadata of sensitive data.
- The most relevant UNESCO OS pillar: open scientific knowledge (please see Figure 2 in the Abbreviations and definitions section).

Examples of the types of contributions to consider:

- Open access publications
- Multilingualism in publications
- Preprints
- Self-archiving in open repositories, discipline specific and institutional
- Open datasets
- Use of open datasets
- Use of FAIR principles
- Shared metadata

- Open code
- Open methods
- Open software
- Use of open software and tools
- Funding for OS activities
- OS as a research topic

Please see also **GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>

Module 2 – People

Prompts:

- R4R: How have you contributed to the development of individuals?
- R4RI: The development of others and maintenance of effective working relationships

Tips:

- Demonstrate your commitment to share your knowledge of OS practices and your role in supporting others in adopting the OS approach.
- Have you taken steps to be inclusive in your approach to managing or mentoring? If so, explain how you have done so.
- The most relevant UNESCO OS pillars: open scientific knowledge, open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems (please see Figure 2 in the Abbreviations and definitions section).

Examples of the types of contributions to consider:

- Open educational resources
- Use of open learning resources
- Open on-line courses
- OS training
- OS in the content of teaching
- Openness on contributorship
- Publication of co-author statements
- Being a role-model in practicing OS
- Training and mentoring other researchers in OS
- Supporting early-career researchers to adopt OS approach
- Raising awareness of OS in undergraduate and masters' programs
- Successfully delivering OS projects involving diverse teams
- Acknowledging and rewarding the use of OS practices as a leader

Module 3 – Community

Prompts:

- R4R: How have you contributed to the wider research community?
- R4RI: Contributions to the wider research and innovation community

Cite as: Koivisto, Elina, & Sipola, Tiina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>

Tips:

- Demonstrate with concrete examples your commitment to open and transparent practices throughout the research process in the wider research community context.
- The most relevant UNESCO OS pillar: open science infrastructures (please see Figure 2 in the Abbreviations and definitions section).

Examples of the types of contributions to consider:

- Open peer review
- Assessing open research
- Contributing as an editor in a community-driven OA-journal
- Participating in OS networks and communities
- Adopting open infrastructure
- Developing general or field-specific OS guidelines
- Driving policy and practice in OS
- Developing a profile for OS activities
- Practicing and promoting multilingualism in scholarly communication

Module 4 – Society

Prompts:

- R4R: How have you contributed to broader society?
- R4RI: Contributions to broader research/innovation-users and audiences and towards wider societal benefit

Tips:

- Demonstrate with concrete examples your commitment to open and transparent practices throughout the research process in the broader society context.
- The most relevant UNESCO OS pillar: open engagement of societal actors and open dialogue with other knowledge systems (please see Figure 2 in the Abbreviations and definitions section).

Examples of the types of contributions to consider:

- Sharing research results through non-academic dissemination channels
- Translating research into suitable language for general public
- Multilingualism in science communication
- Communication about OS to audiences outside of academia
- Participating in public engagement activities
- Implementing participatory science
- Actively engaging stakeholders in research process
- Recognition of contributions of all collaborators (including citizens)
- Engaging in open innovation with partners beyond academia
- Evidence of use of open research by societal groups

Please see also **GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>

RRA and narrative CVs

Benefits and challenges of narrative CVs for researchers

A narrative CV can be an opportunity for a researcher to demonstrate a variety of contributions and activities, including OS contributions. It is a flexible and adaptable tool for different disciplines and career stages, and it can be used to highlight how a researcher has communicated ideas and research results, both written and verbally. In a narrative CV a researcher can highlight how the OS and FAIR principles have been followed and implemented.

Funding bodies and universities across Europe have recently begun to implement narrative CV formats for evaluative decision-making in peer review panels. Narrative CVs supplement traditional information such as publication lists and employment history with novel elements, in which researchers describe their achievements and trajectories in narrative form.

For researchers, narrative CVs enable substantive descriptions of careers and achievements. For evaluators narrative CVs offer a tool for rethinking and thoroughly reconsidering the criteria used to assess and compare applicants (RoRI, 2024). Narrative CVs are important for qualitative assessment which is the primary method for assessment of an individual researcher. However, narrative CVs are just one piece of the puzzle in reforming OS aware RRA and implementation takes time to adjust.

Using narrative CVs also includes challenges, which include for example disadvantage non-native speakers or individuals less skilled at narrative writing. According to the Cancer Research UK (2024) analysis, there are concerns like a *“potential disadvantage to researchers who are either introverted, identify as neurodivergent (variation in mental functions), and/or do not speak English as their first language”*.

Additionally, both writing and evaluating narrative CVs can be more time-consuming than those of traditional CVs. Researchers need training and guidance to become familiar with narrative CVs and thus better able to make use of their features.

Leptin (2024) highlights that *“The narrative format could be used to misrepresent achievements or skills, and different cultures have different norms and expectations around ‘storytelling’ and self-presentation. Therefore, narrative CVs could inadvertently disadvantage individuals from cultures where self-promotion or certain forms of storytelling are not the norm. Writing a compelling narrative CV requires strong writing skills. Therefore, narrative CVs could inadvertently disadvantage individuals who are less skilled or comfortable with writing, even if they are highly skilled in their field of research”*.

Eventually, researchers have the responsibility for selecting research outputs and elements with factual explanations. Other actors, like funders on the other hand, have the responsibility of providing

adequate guidance for both applicants and evaluators on how to write and how to assess narrative CVs.

Below is a list of some examples and experiences of European research funders who have already adopted narrative CVs:

- **European Research Council (ERC)**. Leptin (2024). Evaluation of research proposals: the why and what of the ERC's recent changes. European Research Council (ERC) in https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-02/Evaluation_of_research_proposals.pdf, cited 23 April 2025
- **The Dutch Research Council (NWO)** introduced narrative CV in the Veni in 2019 as part of NWO Talent Programme and is gradually being adopted in other NWO funding instruments. By 2023, the form has evolved into the evidence-based CV. [Read more](#)
- **Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)** introduced a narrative-style CV template for Principal Investigators (PIs) and Co-PIs requesting funding from FNR programmes, currently called the “Individual Narrative Profile”. There were two purposes for this change: a streamlining and simplification of our process, as well as a move towards aligning with the principles of DORA, CoARA and the goals of responsible research assessment. [Read more](#)
- **Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)** is implementing narrative CV to align with DORA principles and is changing the way SFI assesses researchers for funding through the use of a narrative CV and novel scoring methodology. [Read more](#)
- **The Swiss National Science Foundation** is testing a structured narrative CV format called ‘SciCV’ to increase consistency in decision-making for its grant applications. The switch to a more narrative format is designed to help researchers clearly communicate their most important research contributions, rather than relying on a publication list to convey the value of their work. The use of narrative also helps in recognizing and rewarding a variety of research outputs in addition to peer-reviewed articles. SciCV integrates with ORCID making it easy for researchers with an ORCID ID to populate and maintain. [Read more](#)

The role of research funders and research performing organisations

Research funding organisations and research performing organisations have a major role in shaping academic culture. As Mcleod (2014) says,

“Funders and academic institutions do much to set the social and cultural context in which research occurs, and academia’s reward and promotion systems shape the choices of scientists at all stages of their career.”

(RoRI), Research on Research Institute (2025) highlights that: *“for Narrative CVs to achieve their potential, funders need to create an environment that supports and facilitates their use”*.

Some practical issues regarding the use of narrative CVs in research(er) assessment generally discussed are, e.g. time pressure, group dynamics of reviewers, information provided to reviewers and the vulnerability of review panels to various forms of bias.

According to the Cancer Research UK (2024) analysis, half of the reviewers (48 %) had no concerns whatsoever, but there were some issues that became apparent. Of reviewers, 9 % and 7 % felt that the narrative CV is 'less clear than the traditional CV' and 'more time-consuming/wordy', respectively.

RoRI's recommendations for funders

(RoRI), Research on Research Institute (2025) gives five recommendations for implementing narrative CVs. The recommendations are directed for funders but can be applied for other actors who engage narrative CVs in researcher assessment.

1. **Pick the right chair and brief them.** It is critical to ensure that scientific panel chairs are aligned with the commitments and values of funders in relation to the use of narrative CVs.
2. **Offer live instructions to all stakeholders who assess narrative CVs** (like panellists and reviewers) either in a presentation or a video. It is important for funders to spell out their intended use of narrative CVs and explain their reasons for introducing a narrative format.
3. **Make sure that programme evaluation criteria align with intended uses of narrative CVs.** To prevent conflicts or inconsistencies between evaluation criteria and the narrative CV format, funders should carefully review both to ensure their clear alignment. For example, they should avoid situations where formal criteria emphasize traditional markers of excellence (such as publications, grants, and individual achievements) while the narrative CV encourages showcasing collaborative work and societal relevance.
4. **Seek dialogue about resistance to narrative CVs.** We advise funders to ensure that such resistance is not primarily expressed during the meetings of review panels. We therefore recommend creating alternative fora for discussion and fostering dialogue in advance.
5. **Diversify review panels.** Attempts to diversify evaluation criteria should be accompanied by continued efforts to diversify review panels

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University of Oxford. Developing a narrative CV: guidance for researchers. <https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/learn-more-about-developing-a-narrative-cv>

Useful links

DORA Resource library

Keyword “narrative”. https://sfdora.org/resource-library/?_keyword=narrative

PEP-CV. Seek mentor or mentor others on how to structure a narrative CV

The Peer Exchange Platform for Narrative-style CVs (PEP-CV) is a resource for the research and innovation community developed by a partnership between funding agencies and researchers. The goal of PEP-CV is to become a platform for everyone active in the research and innovation sector to engage in simple peer mentoring exchanges to discuss how to best present a diverse range of experiences, achievements, and career paths in all types of narrative-style CVs. PEP-CV is supported by Marie Curie alumni Association, The Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR), Young Academy of Europe, Dutch Research Council, Taighde Éireann – Research Ireland, Swiss National Science Foundation and Wellcome. <https://pep-cv.mariecuriealumni.eu/>

The YUFERING Academic Assessment Portfolio

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In the Horizon 2020-funded project **YUFERING (YUFE Transforming Research and Innovation through Europe-wide Knowledge Transfer)**, a narrative portfolio pilot model has been developed to support researcher evaluation. **The YUFERING Academic Assessment Portfolio**, which resembles a narrative CV template, presents a model for assessing researchers, including their contributions to Open Science (OS). The YUFE Academic Assessment Portfolio is accompanied by a set of good practices for evaluating researchers' contributions in line with the principles of Open Science and the CoARA principles outlined in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA).

See project deliverables:

- YUFE Open Science Model and guidelines for researchers' evaluation.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10131114>
- Report on the accreditation pilot based in Open Science criteria.
<https://zenodo.org/records/10640319>

How to: Write impact statements with Altmetric data

<https://www.altmetric.com/blog/how-to-write-impact-statements-with-altmetric-data/> . Altmetric.com, a Digital Science Solution. Page updated March 24th, 2022, cited 23th April 2025

Guidance for writing a narrative CV

Murray, Kate with input and feedback from Research Facilitators across the University of Cambridge, particularly Naomi Hilton, designed by Marie Collier (2024). **Guidance for writing a narrative CV**. ARRC February 2024, in https://www.rrc.group.cam.ac.uk/files/media/rrc_ncv_resource.pdf , cited 23th April 2025

Research Impact Toolkit

University College Dublin, UCD in <https://www.ucd.ie/impacttoolkit/>, 2025, cited 23th April 2025

Appendix: OS-CAM

Figure 1. Open Science Career Assessment Matrix (OS-CAM) representing the range of evaluation criteria for assessing Open Science activities

Open Science Career Assessment Matrix (OS-CAM)	
Open Science activities	Possible evaluation criteria
RESEARCH OUTPUT	
Research activity	Pushing forward the boundaries of open science as a research topic
Publications	Publishing in open access journals Self-archiving in open access repositories
Datasets and research results	Using the FAIR data principles Adopting quality standards in open data management and open datasets Making use of open data from other researchers
Open source	Using open source software and other open tools Developing new software and tools that are open to other users
Funding	Securing funding for open science activities
RESEARCH PROCESS	
Stakeholder engagement / citizen science	Actively engaging society and research users in the research process Sharing provisional research results with stakeholders through open platforms (e.g. Arxiv, Figshare) Involving stakeholders in peer review processes
Collaboration and Interdisciplinarity	Widening participation in research through open collaborative projects Engaging in team science through diverse cross-disciplinary teams
Research integrity	Being aware of the ethical and legal issues relating to data sharing, confidentiality, attribution and environmental impact of open science activities Fully recognizing the contribution of others in research projects, including collaborators, co-authors, citizens, open data providers
Risk management	Taking account of the risks involved in open science
SERVICE AND LEADERSHIP	
Leadership	Developing a vision and strategy on how to integrate OS practices in the normal practice of doing research Driving policy and practice in open science
	Being a role model in practicing open science

Academic standing	Developing an international or national profile for open science activities Contributing as editor or advisor for open science journals or bodies
Peer review	Contributing to open peer review processes Examining or assessing open research
Networking	Participating in national and international networks relating to open science
RESEARCH IMPACT	
Communication and Dissemination	Participating in public engagement activities Sharing research results through non-academic dissemination channels Translating research into a language suitable for public understanding
IP (patents, licenses)	Being knowledgeable on the legal and ethical issues relating to IPR Transferring IP to the wider economy
Societal impact	Evidence of use of research by societal groups Recognition from societal groups or for societal activities
Knowledge exchange	Engaging in open innovation with partners beyond academia
TEACHING AND SUPERVISION	
Teaching	Training other researchers in open science principles and methods Developing curricula and programs in open science methods, including open science data management Raising awareness and understanding in open science in undergraduate and masters' programs
Mentoring	Mentoring and encouraging others in developing their open science capabilities
Supervision	Supporting early stage researchers to adopt an open science approach
PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	
Continuing professional development	Investing in own professional development to build open science capabilities
Project management	Successfully delivering open science projects involving diverse research teams
Personal qualities	Demonstrating the personal qualities to engage society and research users with open science Showing the flexibility and perseverance to respond to the challenges of conducting open science

